

REPRESENTATION OF THE NATIONAL SPIRIT IN THE NATIONAL IDEA

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During the years of independence, a solid foundation was laid for the formation and development of the national idea. In these matters, of course, it is impossible not to mention the merits of our President. In a number of his works and speeches, the President has repeatedly stressed the importance of the national idea, its harmony with the spirit of the Uzbek people.

Human thinking creates various thoughts, views, ideas and teachings in the process of perceiving reality. Consequently, ideas are also a product of human thinking. But no thought or view, opinion or point of view that creates thinking can be an idea. Only the strongest, most influential, most convincing thoughts can be an idea.

The idea is that important problems that need and need to be solved include a system of tasks and in many ways have a promising character.

Ideology is a system of ideas expressing the needs, goals and aspirations, socio-spiritual principles of a particular social group and class, nation or state, as well as methods and means of their implementation.

It is also spiritual to understand that Uzbekistan is the only country in the world that unites all Uzbeks and is able to protect their interests and dignity. Our sincere compatriots abroad are also proud of Uzbekistan's achievements and suffer when the country is going through.

It is not enough to hear a national idea by ear, you need to feel and understand it with your heart. As a person grows up, his faith in national ideas, national culture, lifestyle, traditions and customs associated with them will continue to grow stronger. Young people understand the national idea, relying mainly on education.

The influence of national ideas in the hearts of the Uzbek people during the reign of Amir Temur has not completely disappeared. They have expanded, enriched, diversified and improved based on the conditions, needs and opportunities of the new era. Due to the fact that representatives of the same ethnic group have been separated from each other for a long time and live in different countries, local sentiments also play an important role in their consciousness and beliefs. This is also a factor that negatively affects the unity of representatives of one nation around a common idea. The fact that Uzbeks sometimes indulge in localism and are divided into Ferghana, Tashkent, Samarkand, Khorezm, etc., the weakness of national ideology in the minds of some groups is a sign that they do not fully understand the unity of national history, destiny, economic, political and spiritual interests.

Another important principle of the national idea is the historical memory of our people, their boundless respect and pride for their Homeland and people. This factor has always been a priority in the national ideology of the Uzbek people. This is because Uzbekistan is our only historical homeland. Our ancestors have lived on this sacred land for centuries, and our umbilical cord blood has been shed. Our future generations will live on this earth. For a

person, there is one Homeland, and one homeland. According to the beliefs of our people, the choice of the Motherland is patriotic.

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